

or alternate path.

The formation of hypobromite ester ($R-CH_2-O-Br$) in the rate determining step (as suggested by Banerji and Negi¹⁰) may be excluded considering the values of entropy of activation. Hence, the proposed reaction mechanism for the oxidation of primary alcohol with NBB is very consistent with the experimental findings.

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Synthesis of Steroidal Oxazolidinone

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OXAZOLIDINONE derivatives have been proved to possess a variety of biological activities, such as antidepressant¹, antibacterial², fungicidal^{3,4}, herbicidal⁵, analgesic⁶, antiinflammatory¹, muscle-relaxant^{1,7} and anticonvulsant^{7,8}. These physiological properties prompted us to undertake the synthetic studies of steroidal oxazolidinones. For this objective, 3 α ,4 α -epoxy-6-nitrocholest-5-ene (1)⁹ was used

as the starting material. When the epoxide (1) was treated with phenylisocyanate in *N,N*-dimethylformamide, the *trans*-dihydroxy compound (2) and the desired oxazolidinone (3) were obtained. The structures of these products were established from chemical analysis and spectral data. The epoxide (1) on treatment with acrylamide under similar reaction conditions also provided the same hydroxy compound (2) and oxazolidinone (3).

Experimental

All melting points were determined on a Kofler's block apparatus and are uncorrected. Ir spectra (nujol) were recorded on a Pye-Unicam sp 3-100 spectrophotometer. Nmr spectra ($CDCl_3$) were run on a Varian A-60D instrument using TMS as internal standard. Light petroleum refers to the fraction b p 60–80°.

Reaction of 3 α ,4 α -epoxy-6-nitrocholest-5-ene (1) with phenylisocyanate- $AlCl_3$: 3 α ,4 α -Epoxy-6-nitrocholest-5-ene⁹ (1; 1.5 g) in *N,N*-dimethylformamide (25 ml) was refluxed with phenylisocyanate (1 ml) ($AlCl_3$ added as catalyst) for 20 min. After the completion of the reaction, it was worked up in ether. The ethereal solution was washed with water and dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. Evaporation of the solvent provided an oil which was chromatographed over a column of silica gel (30g). Elution with petroleum-ether (8:1) provided a solid compound 2, recrystallised from light petroleum, (300 mg), m.p. 120° (Found: C, 72.48; H, 10.06; N, 3.18. $C_{27}H_{45}NO_4$ requires: C, 72.48; H, 10.06; N, 3.13%); ν_{max} 3410 (OH), 1640 (C=C), 1530 and 1370 cm^{-1} (C-NO₂); δ 4.45 (1H, d, J 4Hz, C4- α H), 4.03 (1H, mc, $W_{1/2}$ 7Hz, C3- β H), 2.65 (OH), 1.28 (C10-CH₃), 0.68 (C13-CH₃), 0.92 and 0.82 (other angular methyl protons).

Further elution with light petroleum-ether (4:1) yielded 3, recrystallised from light petroleum (400 mg) m.p. 137° (Found: C, 71.09; H, 9.39; N, 5.88; $C_{28}H_{44}N_2O_4$ requires: C, 71.18; H, 9.32; N, 5.89%); ν_{max} 3420 br (NH) 1725 (oxazolidinone moiety), 1650 (C=C), 1525 and 1365 cm^{-1} (C-NO₂). δ 8.01 (1H, s, NH, exchangeable with D_2O), 5.48 (1H, d, J 3Hz C4- β H), 3.98 (1H, mc, $W_{1/2}$ 7Hz, C3- β H), 1.20 (C10-CH₃), 0.66 (C13-CH₃), 0.88 and 0.78 (remaining methyl protons).

Reaction of 3 α ,4 α -epoxy-6-nitrocholest-5-ene (1) with acrylamide- $AlCl_3$: 3 α ,4 α -epoxy-6-nitrocholest-5-ene⁹ (1; 1.5 g) in *N,N*-dimethylformamide (25 ml)

